

ZHANG XIANG'S FIRST MARCH TO CENTRAL ASIA AND BUDDHISM A LINE TO SPREAD

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Cultural relations between Central Asia and China are directly related to political and economic processes. Relations between Uzbekistan and the People's Republic of China Today, no one can deny that the relations between the two countries have a history of several thousand years due to the fact that the territory of Uzbekistan is the crossroads of the Great Silk Road.

No one thought that the Chinese ambassador Zhang Xiang's first visit to our country would be of great importance in the establishment of relations in this way. The arrival of Zhang Xiang to the ancient (128 BC) state of Fergana (Daiyuan) was another blessing of God to this country. This event can be considered the beginning of diplomatic relations between the two countries. When Zhang Xian returned to his country after a long journey, the Chinese got information not only about Ferghana and the whole of Central Asia. Zhang Xiang is also known as the person who opened the Great Silk Road to the west. The number of ambassadors and Buddhist monks who entered the territory of Uzbekistan after Zhang Xian increased may be due to the fact that these two countries have been located at the crossroads of the caravan route for a long time. In addition to trade, there were periods of conflict between the two countries.

For example, for the Fergana vultures, which are considered a means of speed and a measure of wealth in China, the Chinese state attacked the ancient Davan state several times, the war of the Han Empire's troops against Fergana (104-100 BC) and the military campaign of the Tan empire to Tashkent. (in 658 BC) can be an example of this. Along with the development of relations, the spread of foods such as peaches, mash, onions, pumpkin, tandoori bread, and somsa to China was observed.

At the beginning of the 3rd century, the Han Empire (206 BC - 220 AD) lost its position in China. The internal struggles in the country have escalated to the extreme, and even the national idea in the society has weakened. In such a situation, the need for a new doctrine increased. The highly developed Buddhist teachings in Central

Asia corresponded to the demands of Chinese society. As a result, ambassadors and merchants from the Kushan state and neighboring countries went to China with a large amount of gifts and goods. They were the propagators of Buddhism and were active in spreading the teachings of Buddhism in Chinese society. There were even Turkestan monks who devoted their lives to the propagation of Buddhism in China. The Chinese communicated with the monks from Turan and had difficulty pronouncing their names. Therefore, the Chinese shortened the name of the guests or gave the name of their country as a surname. According to the recognition of most Chinese scholars, in the history of ancient Chinese dynasties, it was during the Eastern Han Dynasty that many foreigners came to China, among them the influence of Central Asians. A number of Chinese went to the palace of Kadphiz (ruled 26-44 AD) and spread Buddhism.

In conclusion, it should be noted that when Zhang Xiang returned to his country after a long journey, the Chinese not only had information about Ferghana and the whole of Central Asia. It is appropriate that they are also known as the person who opened the way. That is, the Buddha was the propagator of the Buddhist religion, who showed enthusiasm in spreading the Buddhist teachings in the Chinese society.

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References:

1. Isayev, O. (2019). THE CULTURAL LIFE IN SURKHAN OASIS: INFORMING OF ACHIEVEMENTS AND PROBLEMS BASED ON ARCHIVAL MATERIALS (1925–1941 YEARS). *The Light of Islam*, 2019(4), 31.
2. Tojimurodovich, Q. N. (2023). Administrative Structure and Management System of the Becks in Surkhan Oasis. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY*, 4(10), 87-92.
3. Tojimurodovich, Q. N. (2022). BUXORO AMIRLIGIDA SURXON VOHASI BEKLIKLARI. INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. *SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL*, 3(9), 36-39.
4. NAMOZ, Q. (2022). THE HISTORY OF MADRASAH SAID OTALIQ. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 10-13.
5. Isaev, O. A. (2021). Contradictory processes in the reform of agriculture in the Surkhandarya oasis in the 20-30s of the XX century. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), 942-946.

6. Исаев, О. А., & Сафаров, Б. С. (2020). Проблемы здравоохранения в Сурхандарьинской области (1925-1941 гг.). Бюллетень науки и практики, 6(11), 433-438.

7. Oybek, P. I. (2022). In the Study of the History of Surkhandarya in the 30s of the XX Century, as a Historical Source. Eurasian Journal of History, Geography and Economics, 7, 100-102.

8. Isaev, O. A. (2021). Contradictory processes in the reform of agriculture in the Surkhandarya oasis in the 20-30s of the XX century. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(9), 942-946.

9. Qudratov, N., Xudoyorov, A., & Oltiyev, A. (2024). BUXORO AMIRLIGIDA SURXON VOHASIDAGI BEKLIKLARINING MA'MURIY TUZILISHI VA BOSHQARUV TIZMI. " Science Shine" International scientific journal, 15(1).